

A REVIEW ON SYNTHESIS OF BIOACTIVE PYRANOPYRAZOLES BY ONE POT MULTICOMPONENT STRATEGIES

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Abstract

An environment friendly one pot three-component reaction of an aromatic aldehydes, 3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one and malononitrile or one pot four-component reaction of an aromatic aldehydes, ethylacetoacetate, phenyl hydrazine and malononitrile in alcoholic/ aqua medium in the presence of acidic, alkaline, nanometals and ionic liquids as catalysts has been designed for synthesis of bioactive pyranopyrazole heterocyclic compounds. Pyranopyrazoles shows tremendous biological and medicinal properties and synthesis of these bioactive heterocycles has fascinated the interest of pharmacist and organic chemists. This review focuses on the recent developments in multi-component synthesis of pyranopyrazole reactions among aromatic aldehyde, malononitrile and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one. The present review describes the literature reports from the past decade.

Keywords: Ambient temperature, Green conditions, MCRs, Pyranopyrazole, Reusable catalysts.

Introduction

Pyranopyrazole containing heterocyclic compounds shows superior roles in medicinal and synthetic chemistry. Polyfunctionalized 4H-pyran has fascinated the attentions of many researchers included in drug discovery process [1-3], because of its pharmacological and biological features[4]. Pyranopyrazole compounds which are oxygen and nitrogen ring fused heterocycles, are prime important group of heterocyclic compounds with natural and synthetic molecules [5]. They showed large number of biological activities such as antibacterial [6], anti-microbial [7-8], anticancer [9], anti-inflammatory and analgesic [10], hypnotic, antitumor [11], and molluscicidal[12] properties. Synthesis of the heterocyclic compounds containing the pyranopyrazole moiety is of huge importance. There are four isomeric structures for pyranopyrazole involving: pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazole, pyrano[3,2-c]pyrazole, pyrano[3,4-c]pyrazole, and pyrano[4,3-c]pyrazole. Out of these four isomers plethora amount of work has been done on pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazole due to its biological activity and use in medicines. Several synthetic pathways have been reported to prepare these biologically precious pyranopyrazole heterocycles. This short review focusses on one pot multicomponent reactions of three-components and four-components for the synthesis of pyranopyrazole. In multicomponent reactions (MCRs) target product was obtained without separation and purification of the intermediates which is the main benefit in comparison with traditional, protocols [13]. MCRs have high efficiency, experimental simplicity, low cost, minimum generation of waste, minimizing labour cost, less reaction times, better atom economy [14]. These are superior to tedious multi step protocols in several aspects including the simplicity of a one-pot procedure, possible structural variations and building up complex molecules. Taking into consideration these advantages of MCRs, in this review we have summarized the reported protocols for the preparation of pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazole derivatives by multicomponent reactions(MCRs) utilizing solvents like ethanol, water and catalysts like acidic, basic, nano-metals, ionic liquids, along with conventional conditions or by using microwaves or ultrasound irradiation.

Hasaninejada *et al.* [15] synthesized a series of pyrano-[2,3-c]-pyrazole analogues in the presence of SiO₂ supported n-propyl-4-aza-1-azoniabicyclo-[2.2.2]-octane chloride(SB-DABCO). The multicomponent reaction was carried out using various substituted aldehydes, active methylene compounds and 3-methyl-pyrazolone in Ethanol as solvent medium. Authors claimed that 90–98% yields

were obtained using 6 mol% of SB-DABCO catalyst at ambient temperature for about 35min. This protocol offered high yields with various active methylene compounds. (Scheme-1)

Scheme -1

The nano $\text{TiO}_2/\text{H}_{14}[\text{NaP}_5\text{W}_{30}\text{O}_{110}]$ catalyzed three-component reaction (Scheme-2) of malononitrile, aromatic aldehydes, 3-methyl-pyrazolinone via ultrasound irradiation at 40°C in ethanol solvent medium was reported by Azarifar and coworkers [16]. The target dihydropyrano [2,3 c]pyrazoles were synthesized at higher yields due to the larger surface area of nano catalyst particles. The catalyst's structure was characterized and confirmed by BET and TEM analysis. TEM analysis results suggested the presence of nanoparticles with an average size (15–50 nm) and BET-specific surface area ($175\text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$).

Scheme-2

Irvani along with colleagues [17] synthesized tin sulfide nanoparticles on activated carbon [SnS-NPs@AC] and used them as a catalyst for preparing pyrano-[2, 3-c]-pyrazoles. The reported MCR (Scheme-3) of 3-methyl-pyrazolinone, various aldehydes, malononitrile and catalyst in ethanol solvent led to the desired compounds at 80°C in about 25 min reaction time. The nanocatalyst maintained its activity for several cycles. The mechanistic scheme included Knoevenagel condensation, Michael-type addition, and cyclisation to yield the target products.

Scheme-3

One-pot, rapid synthesis of pyrano[2, 3-c]-pyrazole derivatives by utilizing amino-functionalized SBA-15 (SBA-Pr-NH₂) catalyst was reported by Zainali *et al.* [18]. The reaction was performed using aryl aldehyde, malononitrile, phenyl hydrazine and ethyl acetoacetate in ethanol at RT and obtained the higher yields (Scheme-4). Authors also provided plausible mechanism suggesting that the intermediate formed through Knoevenagel condensation of phenyl hydrazine with ethyl acetoacetate, then underwent Michael addition with arylmethlidene malononitrile to afford the target molecules.

Scheme-4

Salehi and group of scientists [19] reported one-pot synthesis of two series of pyrano [2,3-*c*]-pyrazoles and spiro-pyrano[2,3-*c*]-pyrazoles applying a nano SiO₂-supported 1,4-diazabicyclo-[2.2.2]-octane (nano SiO₂/DABCO) catalyst. The SEM-EDX characterization provided that the synthesized SiO₂/DABCO nanomaterial contained C, Cl, N, O and Si elements. The catalytic activity was observed on the multicomponent reaction of the beta-keto ester, substituted hydrazine, malononitrile and aldehyde in the absence of solvent at RT via the grinding method (Scheme-5). The reaction proceeded in several steps, involving Knoevenagel condensation and Michael addition, followed by intramolecular cyclisation to give product.

Scheme -5

Abbasabadi *et al.* [20] mentioned the sulfonic acid-mobilized Fe₃O₄-graphene oxide magnetic catalyst (Fe₃O₄@GO) for the synthesis of pyrano [2,3-*c*]-pyrazoles through the one-step, multicomponent reaction of 3-methyl-pyrazolone, malononitrile and different substituted aldehyde in ethanol at ambient temperature. The catalyst acted significantly and afforded excellent product yields with lower reaction time (Scheme 6). Heteroaromatic and alkyl aldehydes had longer reaction times and gave lesser yields, as compared to the aromatic aldehydes. They further recovered the catalyst from the reaction mixture using a magnet.

Scheme -6

Heravi *et al.* [21] reported the preparation of dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*] pyrazole scaffolds using Preyssler-type hetero polyacid (H₁₄[NaP₅W₃₀O₁₁₀]) as a reusable catalyst through a one-pot reaction. A multicomponent reaction employed malononitrile, a variety of aldehydes and 3-methyl-pyrazolone at refluxing conditions for 60 min. with 1 mol% of catalyst effectively performed under ethanol/water media (Scheme 7). Authors also examined the different active methylene compounds (diethyl malonate, ethyl acetoacetate, ethyl cyanoacetate, ethyl benzoyl acetate and acetophenone) under similar reaction conditions. The protocol was only dynamic with malononitrile. The reaction progressed via Knoevenagel condensation, Michael addition and was followed by intramolecular cyclisation to form the desired product. As mentioned by authors excellent yields, reusability, simple workup procedure and use of green solvents were the benefits of this protocol.

Scheme-7

Zolfigol and his coworkers [22] successfully synthesized an efficient and stable nano-Fe₃O₄@SiO₂@(CH₂)₃-Imidazole-SO₃HCl as a magnetic catalyst. The activity of the nanocatalyst was assessed on the three-component reaction of varieties of aldehydes, malononitrile, and 3-methyl-pyrazolone to synthesize dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles derivatives under solvent-free conditions (Scheme-8). Both aromatic and heteroaromatic aldehydes, bearing electron-donating or electron-withdrawing

groups, were well tolerated and gave the products. The nanocatalyst was recovered by simple magnetic separation and reutilized for further cycles with a minor loss of activity.

Scheme -8

The mesoporous catalyst ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@\text{FSM-16-SO}_3\text{H}$) for the preparation of new dihydropyrano-[2, 3-*c*]-pyrazole scaffolds was proposed by Uderji *et al.* [23]. The target molecules were prepared by a multicomponent reaction between malononitrile, 3-methyl-pyrazolone and aldehydes in the presence of 30 mg catalyst in a water-ethanol system at reflux condition (Scheme-9).

Scheme – 9

A facile, three-component reaction of malononitrile, 3-methyl-pyrazolinone, and aromatic aldehydes forming pyranopyrazole derivatives progressed well under a solvent-free condition in 2 hrs at 80 °C with the help of a low catalytic amount of $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@\text{TiO}_2@(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{OWO}_3\text{H}$ via one-pot process [24]. The MCR progressed smoothly, with a domino Knoevenagel and Michael addition via cyclisation reaction (Scheme-10).

Scheme-10

In 2013, lanthanum strontium magnesium oxide ($\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{MnO}_3$ (LSMO)) was used as a mixed heterogeneous catalyst by Azarifar and fellows [25]. Use of 5 mol% of LSMO catalyst material promoted the synthesis of pyrano-[2,3-*c*]-pyrazole scaffolds under ultrasound irradiation conditions from the reaction between malononitrile, aromatic aldehydes and 3-methyl-pyrazolinone in ethanol medium (Scheme -11).

Scheme-11

Malekil *et al.* [26] demonstrated a number of pyrano[2,3-*c*]-pyrazoles and tetrahydrobenzopyran using an effective silica-coated magnetic catalyst ($\text{NiFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{SiO}_2\text{-H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$; NFS-PWA) as a heterogeneous acidic catalyst. The nanocatalyst showed high efficacy in the three-component reaction of 3-methyl-pyrazolinone, active methylene compound, and various functional groups substituted aldehydes under ethanol solvent conditions. The catalyst material showed matching activity for five runs and offered excellent yields of both the tetrahydrobenzopyran and pyranopyrazole derivatives within a short reaction time (Scheme -12).

Scheme-12

Azarifar and his group members [27] prepared a novel γ -Fe₂O₃@Cu₃Al-LDH-TUD material which showed superior catalytic activity in the synthesis of new dihydropyranopyrazoles from the corresponding 3-methylphenylpyrazolinone, malononitrile, and substituted aldehyde at 100 °C for 45 min under solvent-free conditions. Similarly, this protocol proved good with 4-hydroxy coumarins for the preparation of dihydropyrano [3,2-*c*]-chromenes with significant yields (75–93%) (Scheme-13). The multicomponent reaction was subjected to the steric and electronic influences connected with various substituents on aldehydes. Reportedly, the sequence initiated by malononitrile and aldehyde reacted to generate an intermediate via Knoevenagel condensation. In the follow-up, the Michael addition of 3-methylphenylpyrazolinone to the intermediate delivered the preferred target molecule.

Scheme-13

In 2017, Nazari and his colleagues [28] developed a novel amberlite-supported L-prolinate ([Amb]L-prolinate). The material showed good catalytic efficacy in synthesizing pyrano-[2,3-*c*]-pyrazole scaffolds through the one-pot approach. The multicomponent condensation reaction, included malononitrile, 3-methyl-pyrazolinone and number substituted aldehydes under ethanol medium at reflux conditions, afforded excellent yields (85–98%) of the target molecules within a short reaction time (<25 min), employing 10 mol% [Amb]L-prolinate as the catalyst (Scheme -14). The one-pot reaction occurred through the Knoevenagel condensation and Michael addition via cyclisation in sequence. The catalyst was reusable for up to eight cycles with sustained efficiency.

Scheme-14

Mandha et al. [29] have reported a green approach for the synthesis of substituted pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles and spiro-pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles through a multicomponent reaction in aqueous ethanol medium under catalyst-free conditions. The synthesis of pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles via a multicomponent approach under catalyst-free conditions, as shown in (Scheme-15) was envisaged. In the report, when one-pot reaction was developed by replacing one of the substrates that is, hydrazine hydrate with phenyl hydrazine, reaction was too sluggish. In order to improve the rate of reaction, 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-5(4*H*)-one was isolated by performing an initial condensation reaction between ethyl acetoacetate and phenyl hydrazine via a known procedure

Scheme -15

Khazaei et.al.[30] have applied N,2-dibromo-6-chloro-3,4-dihydro-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]thiadiazine-7-sulfonamide-1,1-dioxide (DCDBTSD) as a homogeneous catalyst for the synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyranopyrazoles and spiro-pyranopyrazole by multicomponent reaction in water (Schemes 16). In the report, 4H-pyran, pyranopyrazole, pyrazolo[1,2-b]phthalazine and spirooxindoles were also synthesized by this protocol(Scheme-16).

Scheme-16

Ammonium triflate is an organocatalyst which has been applied in a variety of reactions. Zhou et al.[31] have described a one-pot, four-component reaction of ethyl acetoacetate, hydrazine hydrate, aldehydes, and malononitrile using morpholine triflate (MorT) for preparation of dihydropyranopyrazoles (Scheme -17). Authors tested different kinds of ammonium triflates for the optimization of the reaction conditions. MorT proved to be the most efficient one, giving the highest yield.

Scheme-17

Khurana et al.[32] have discovered a synthetic protocol of 4H-pyranopyrazoles using four-component cyclocondensation of hydrazine monohydrate/phenyl hydrazine, ethyl acetoacetate, aldehydes, and malononitrile in the presence of L-proline and [Bmim]BF₄ at 50 °C (Scheme 18). In this study, the model reaction was carried out using equimolar amount of [Bmim]BF₄ in the presence of different bases (Et₃N, Et₂NH, piperidine, K₂CO₃, L-proline) at 50 °C. [Bmim]BF₄. L-Proline was found as the best catalyst for reaction medium with the highest efficiency at present study.

Scheme-18

1,4-Dimethyl-1-(4-sulphobutyl)piperazinium hydrogen sulfate (IL1), an ionic liquid with both Bronsted acidic and Lewis basic sites was applied to synthesis of pyranopyrazoles at room temperature

under solvent-free conditions. This “green,” homogeneous and reusable catalyst was also used to prepare benzopyran at ambient temperature, amino-2-chromenes and dihydropyrano[*c*]-chromenes at 80 °C under solvent-free conditions[33] (Scheme -19). In addition, the double Bronsted acid, 1,4-dimethyl-1,4-bis(4-sulphobutyl)piperazinium hydrogen sulfate, was synthesized to evaluate the cooperation efficiency of its Bronsted acidic and Lewis basic sites as compared with the double Bronsted acidic sites in IL1.

Scheme-19

Zakeri et al.[34] have applied 1,3-dimethyl-2-oxo-1,3-bis(4-sulfobutyl) imidazolidine-1,3-dium hydrogen sulfate [DMDBSI].2HSO₄ for the four-component reaction of phenyl hydrazine, ethyl acetoacetate, benzaldehyde, and malononitrile to prepare pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles in H₂O at 60 °C (Scheme -20). Authors, in initial experiments, in order to find an effective catalyst and optimize the reaction conditions, screened a series of ILs with respect to both cation and anion counter- parts. They observed that the sulfonic acid ILs actively catalyze the synthesis of desired pyrano [2,3-*c*]pyrazole.

Scheme-20

Heravia et.al.in 2011[35] a four-component reaction of hydrazine hydrate or phenyl hydrazine, ethyl 3-alkyl-3-oxo-propanoate, aldehydes and malononitrile in the presence of nanosized magnesium oxide as a heterogeneous basic catalyst in aceto-nitrile and at ambient temperature for preparation of 6-amino-3-alkyl-4-aryl-5-cyano-1,4- dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles has been reported (Scheme- 21). The reaction was also carried out in the presence of commercially available magnesium oxide (MgO). The catalytic activity of the nanosized MgO particles was compared with the commercially available MgO catalyst. The result showed that the activity of the nanosized MgO was much better, compared to the commercial MgO catalyst.

Scheme-21

Saha and his coworkers [36] have used ZrO₂ nanoparticles as a catalyst in a green solvent (water-ethanol) at room temperature for the preparation of pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole (Scheme-22). The surface of ZrO₂ NPs possibly contains active hydroxyl, oxide and Zr^{b4}, to act as Lewis acids or bases. The catalytic activity and tetragonal plane of the ZrO₂ nanoparticles remained unchanged after the 10th cycle. This protocol was also applied to the synthesis of benzylpyrazolyl coumarins derivatives.

Scheme-22

Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) have reported as attractive solid supports for immobilization of homogeneous catalysts. Cesium carbonate supported on hydroxyapatite coated $\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ magnetic nanoparticles ($\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Hap}-\text{Cs}_2\text{CO}_3$) was used as magnetically separable, green and recyclable heterogeneous catalyst for the synthesis of pyranopyrazole derivatives [37] (Scheme 23). The reactions were carried out at room temperature in 50:50 water/ethanol. $\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Hap}-\text{Cs}_2\text{CO}_3$ was separated from the reaction mixture by external magnetic field and efficiently reused at least six runs without any loss of its catalytic activity.

Scheme-23

In 2015[38] BF_3 bonded nano Fe_3O_4 (BF_3/MNPs), as heterogeneous and reusable catalyst was used for the preparation of 1, 4-dihydropyrano [2,3-*c*]pyrazole derivatives (Scheme- 24). In this report, BF_3/MNPs nanoparticles were prepared at three calcination temperature and characterized by different techniques.

Scheme -24

A biochemical and ecofriendly method was reported for the synthesis of Ag nanoparticles using an aqueous leaf extract of readily accessible *Cinnamomum tamala* as reducing and stabilizing agents[39]. These Ag nanoparticles were utilized to catalyze the synthesis of pyranopyrazoles in water (Scheme-25). The authors extended the reaction scope, by performing the reaction with phenylhydrazine instead of hydrazine hydrate, under similar reaction conditions, the reactions were completed at 60 °C. The green nature and ease of recovery and reusability of the catalyst, are the advantages of this protocol.

Scheme-25

The titanomagnetite nanoparticles ($\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{O}_4$) have been used as support for the preparation of a magnetic acidic catalyst. These nanoparticles were functionalized with sulfonic acid groups in

order to prepare the $\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{O}_4@\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ nanoparticles [40]. The synthesized acidic nanoparticles were used as recyclable heterogeneous catalyst for the synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles (Scheme-26). This catalyst was also utilized for the preparation of 4*H*-chromenes.

Scheme-26

In 2017 [41] zwitterion sulfamic acid functionalized nanoclay (MMT-ZSA) was prepared by montmorillonite K-10 as template, 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane as linker and chlorosulfonic acid as a SO_3H source. MMT-ZSA as a reusable catalyst (five times) was applied to the synthesis of dihydropyrano [2,3-*c*]pyrazoles and spiro[indoline-3,4'-pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole] derivatives via the MCR multicomponent reaction of hydrazine hydrate (or phenyl hydrazine), malononitrile, *b*-keto ester, and carbonyl compounds (1,2-di ketones and Benzaldehyde derivatives) under solvent-free conditions (Scheme-27).

Scheme-27

Arghan and his colleagues [42] have reported deposition of polyacrylamide on nanomagnetite surface via in situ polymerization of acryl amide to form $n\text{-Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{PAM}$ nanocomposite. The amide ($-\text{CONH}_2$) groups could be converted to amine ($-\text{NH}_2$) groups through Hofmann degradation to introduce $n\text{-Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{PVAm}$ as a heterogeneous base catalyst. Authors have applied the obtained organic- inorganic nanocomposite to solvent-free syntheses of dihydropyrano [2,3-*c*]pyrazole derivatives at room temperature (Scheme-28). In the reaction, $n\text{-Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{PVAm}$ nanocomposite with its free primary amino groups behaves as a base catalyst.

Scheme-28

Synthesis of pyranopyrazole derivatives was studied M.J.Nasab et.al. Using *b*-CD/EP as a stationary microvessel and basic heterogeneous catalyst at 100 °C under solvent-free condition [43]*b*-Cyclodextrin-epichlorohydrin nano-sponge polymer, *b*-CD/EP, was prepared by stepwise polymerization of *b*-Cyclodextrin with epi- chlorohydrin under basic conditions(Scheme-29).

Scheme-29

Zakeri *et. al.* [44] have synthesized a novel phosphoric acid functionalized graphene oxide as a water tolerant and highly dispersible carbon-based nanocatalyst for multicomponent synthesis of pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazole yielding 80-90% of products within 15 min in water (Scheme 30)

Scheme-30

Hamrahian *et.al.* [45] have reported superparamagnetic silica-coated Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles immobilized molybdenum Schiff-base complex as recyclable and reusable nanocatalyst for the synthesis of pyranopyrazole derivatives via condensation of aromatic aldehydes, malononitrile and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline-5-one. High to excellent yields, less reaction times, and mild reaction conditions are the features of this protocol (Scheme- 31).

Scheme-31

Chen *and his coworkers* [46] have prepared Ru^{III} incorporated with CMC/Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanocatalyst and investigated its catalytic activity in the synthesis of pyranopyrazole and Polyhydroquinolines derivatives *via* one-pot four-component condensation of aryl aldehyde, malononitrile, hydrazine hydrate and diethyl acetylenedicarboxylate or carbonyl compound, malononitrile, hydrazine hydrate and ethyl aceto(benzoyl) acetate. Broad substrate scope, mild reaction conditions, good-to-excellent yields, operational simplicity, energy-efficiency, high atom-economy, easy isolation of products and no column chromatographic separation, recyclability, reuse for several cycles without significant loss of its activity and easy recovery of Ru^{III}@CMC/Fe₃O₄ are the superior features of this protocol (Scheme -32).

Scheme-32

Zolfigol *et. al.*[47] first time prepared {[HMIM]C(NO₂)₃} nano ionic liquid (NIL), and investigated its catalytic activity in the synthesis of pyranopyrazole derivatives via one pot four

component reactions of various aromatic aldehydes (1 mmol), malononitrile (1 mmol), phenyl hydrazine (1 mmol) and ethyl acetoacetate (1 mmol) in under solvent free at room temperature that is green conditions (Scheme-33).

Scheme-33

Redouane et.al.in 2019[48] synthesized and reported 1,3-dimethyl imidazolium dimethyl phosphate [DMImd-DMP] as a highly efficient and reusable catalyst for the synthesis of pyranopyrazole derivatives via condensation of aromatic aldehydes, malononitrile and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline-5-one in aqueous ethanol (1:1) at reflux conditions (Scheme-34).

Scheme-34

H.Maleki et.al.in 2019[49] reported environmentally benign synthesis of pyranopyrazole derivatives by cobalt Schiff-base complexes immobilized on magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles. They synthesized various derivatives of pyranopyrazole through one pot three component reaction of aromatic aldehydes, malononitrile and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline-5-one by using of heterogeneous catalyst in green solvent (Scheme-35).

Scheme-35

Ghorbani et al.in 2013[50] reported one-pot, four-component reaction of various aromatic aldehydes, malononitrile, phenyl hydrazine and ethyl acetoacetate for synthesis of pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazoles catalyzed by sodium benzoate as an efficient and green catalyst in aqueous medium (scheme-36).

Scheme-36

M. Wu et.al. [51] has been developed an environmentally benign four-component reaction in aqueous medium in the presence of cetyltrimethylammonium chloride (CTACl) for the synthesis of 6-amino-3-methyl-4-aryl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-c]pyrazole-5-carbonitrile. This reaction gives products in good to excellent yields. The benefits of this new method are novelty, good yields, ecofriendliness, and easy workup (scheme-37).

Scheme-37

B. Maleki et.al. [52] Prepared and characterized Nano α -Al₂O₃ supported ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (NH₄H₂PO₄/Al₂O₃) applied this heterogeneous catalyst for one-pot, four-component reaction of various aromatic aldehydes, malononitrile, phenyl hydrazine and ethyl acetoacetate for synthesis of pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazoles in green solvent (Scheme-38).

Scheme-38

T.T.Khatri et.al.in 2017[53] have reported a green approach for the synthesis of pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazoles through a multicomponent reaction in aqueous medium. In the report one pot four component reaction was carried out of various aromatic aldehydes, malononitrile, phenyl hydrazine and ethyl acetoacetate for synthesis of pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazoles by using L-histidine as catalyst in green solvent (Scheme-39)..

Scheme-39

Amin et.al in 2019 [54] reported one-pot four component synthesis of pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazoles from phenyl hydrazine, ethyl acetoacetate, aromatic aldehyde, and malononitrile in the presence of catalytic amounts of a caffeine as a green catalyst in water at 50 °C. In this work he has described advantages of reaction like clean reaction, a short reaction time, a high product yield, and an environmentally-friendly, easily-purified, and economically-available catalyst (Scheme-40).

Scheme-40

Jaberi et.al.in 2013 [55] reported two efficient and convenient methods for the synthesis of pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazoles derivatives based on four-component reaction involving ethyl acetoacetate, phenyl- hydrazine, malononitrile, and various aromatic aldehydes using trichloroacetic acid or ceric

sulfate as heterogeneous catalysts in excellent yields and short reaction times without utility of solvent (Scheme-41).

Scheme-41

Mohamadpour et.al.[56] developed a catalyst-free, green and rapid one-pot four-component reaction of ethyl acetoacetate, phenyl- hydrazine, malononitrile, and various aromatic aldehydes in the presence of ethylene glycol(E-G)catalyst, tandem strategy for the preparation of dihydropyrano[2,3-c]pyrazoles a biologically significant scaffold through Knoevenagel-Michael cyclocondensation based on green chemistry principles(Scheme-42).

Scheme-42

Laroum et.al.in 2017 [57] reported the clean synthesis of pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazoles derivatives by using one pot four component reaction of of commercially available aromatic aldehyde aldehydes, malononitrile, ethyl acetoacetate (or ethyl benzoylacetate), and hydrazine hydrate (or phenyl hydrazine).The reaction was carried out in aqueous ethanol in presence of sodium citrate as a catalyst(Scheme-43).

Scheme-43

Kangani et.al.2013 [58] reported a one-pot four-component synthesis of highly functionalized 1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-c]pyrazoles utilizing phenylhydrazine, ethyl acetoacetate, malononitrile and aryl aldehydes under solvent-free, thermal conditions, with maltose as catalyst, has been developed.In this reaction 81-96% yield was obtained(Scheme-44).

Scheme-44

Azarifar et.al.[59] reported an efficient and convenient procedure for one-pot synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-c]pyrazole derivatives in the presence of nano-titania sulfuric acid (15-nm TSA) as a heterogeneous catalyst.They carried out reaction of three component of aromatic aldehydes, malononitrile and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline-5-one in ethanol and ultrasound. The catalyst was easily prepared from the reaction of nano-titania and chlorosulfonic acid in dichloromethane as solvent. (Scheme-45).

Scheme-45

Sanaeishoar et.al. [60] Prepared hybrid nanocomposite, Fe₂O₃@MCM-BP and applied that alkaline heterogeneous magnetic catalyst for the synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyranopyrazoles via one pot four component reaction of phenylhydrazine, ethyl acetoacetate, malononitrile and aryl aldehydes without using solvent (Scheme-46).

Scheme-46

Albadi et.al.[61] reported synthesis of various pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazoles derivatives via four-component reaction of phenyl hydrazine, ethyl acetoacetate, malononitrile and aromatic aldehydes, catalyzed by basic recyclable poly(4-vinylpyridine) (PVPy). They mentioned advantages such as, atom-economy, easy work up, clean procedure, short reaction times and high yields of products (Scheme-47).

Scheme-47

Shinde et.al. [62] Prepared different pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazoles heterocyclic derivatives by using multicomponent strategies condensation of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one, an aromatic aldehyde, and malononitrile catalyzed by sulfamic acid in ethanol (Scheme-48).

Scheme-48

Khodja et.al.[63] described a simple, efficient and benign method for the dihydropyranopyrazoles synthesis by single pot a four-component condensation between hydrazine (or phenylhydrazine), ethyl acetoacetate, malononitrile and a variety of aromatic aldehydes, catalyzed by Triphenylphosphine (PPh₃) in green solvent at reflux condition (Scheme-49).

Scheme-49

1.3 CONCLUSION

This review has gathered the reported articles regarding synthesis of pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole by one pot three component reactions of aromatic aldehydes, malononitrile and 3-methyl-1-phenyl pyrazolin-5-one and four component reactions of aromatic aldehyde, malononitrile, phenyl hydrazine and ethylacetoacetate by utilizing Multicomponent strategies. Mostly pyranopyrazole bioactive and medicinally functional compounds has been yielded under ecofriendly manner green solvents and environment friendly catalysts. Greener protocols has been employed in the synthesis of target heterocyclic products utilizing catalysts like ionic liquids, acidic, basic and nano catalysts. Similarly using Multicomponent reactions under green chemistry principles in one pot offers good to excellent yields for the preparation of sustainable organic pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole product without generation of toxic wastes.

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